

Core-Team:

Claudia Engelhardt
Linus Hartmann-Enke
Johannes Sperling

SaxFDM – towards a comprehensive research data management support network for Saxony

● SaxFDM – Research data management in saxony

- Bottom-up-initiative consisting of universities, external research facilities and GLAM institutions
- Since 2019
- Open for all data-creating, -archiving and -processing research institutions in Saxony

● Work levels

Working groups

- **Services and tools:** Knowledge exchange, creation of common services
- **Knowledge transfer & consultation:** common knowledge base, development of centralised consultation service
- **Events:** Digital Kitchen, Twitter- and Zenodo channel, website, RDM conference

Plenum

- Decision making body, quarterly meetings

Speakers

- Coordination, representation and management

Scientific Advisory Board

- Strategic evaluation and support

● Project: establishing a cooperative research data management support in the Free state of Saxony

- Funded by the Saxon State Ministry of Science, Culture and Tourism (SMWK)
- Timeline: November 2021 – End of 2025

Diese Maßnahme wird mitfinanziert durch Steuermittel auf der Grundlage des vom Sächsischen Landtag beschlossenen Haushaltes.

Project goals

- State-wide consultation service
- Design of training and education offers
- Further development of the portfolio of technical RDM services based on needs assessment
- Fostering and supporting the implementation of RDM in the policies, guidelines and strategies of the SaxFDM partner institutions
- Development of a business model to sustain SaxFDM activities and structures beyond the end of the project lifetime

Consultation service

- State-wide RDM-consultation service for all Saxon researchers
 - Concerning all topics of the RDM-circle of life

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 - Concerning all topics of the RDM-circle of life
 - Coordination with lokal and regional RDM-departments
 - e.g.: Dezernat 1 University of Leipzig or DRESDEN-concept
 - Cooperation with NFDI-Helpdesks

● Training and education offers

- State-wide education offers
 - Concerning all topics of the RDM-circle of life
 - Target groups: RDM-personnel and Researchers
 - Either online or on-site
 - Create awareness and complement missing services

Technical services

- Support of institutions in the development and deployment of state-wide tools
 - Surveys about needs and wants of services and tools
 - e.g. OpARA

Expert-/NetworkHub

- Networkhub
 - Knowledge about "who works where with what data?"
 - Mutual help and support
 - Knowledge about where knowledge is located
 - Experts for consultations

● Implementation of RDM

- Support of institutions in the implementation of RDM
 - Development of guidelines and policies
 - Structuring internal organisation and their connection to SaxFDM
- RDM-Strategy for Saxony

● Development of a business model

- Development of a business model for SaxFDM
 - Concept of steady continuation needs to be written until the end of 2025
 - Coordination and continuous talks with the institutions and the SMWK

Further goals

- Cooperation and networking of all partner institutions
- Grouping of activities towards a sustainable organisational structure
- Strategic FDM-implementation in all partner institutions
- Establishment as a central partner for support of all Saxon researchers
- Protection and strengthening of Saxony as a research location
- Reinforcement of data literacy / competenz of researchers

Open questions

- Effective interplay between different actors?
- Communication of offers to all reserachers?
- Operating and business model?

Feedback

Thank you very much!

Questions/Feedback

● SaxFDM-Fokusprojekte

SaxFDM-DMP

Konzeption und Pilotierung eines sachsenweiten Services zur **Datenmanagementplanung**

OpARA4Saxony

Ausbau des Forschungsdatenrepositoriums/-archivs OpARA als sachsenweiter Dienst

ANNO

Anthropological Notation Ontology

Pudel

Publikationsdienst für wissenschaftliche **Datenmodelle** und **Vokabulare**